

Supplementary Data 1

In 250 μL serum, 10 μL deuterated internal standard (androstenedione-d7, CDN Isotopes, Pointe-Claire, QC, Canada) was added. Subsequently, androstenedione was extracted with 1 mL methyl tert-butyl ether and dried using a SpeedVac concentrator. Dried samples were reconstituted in 100 μL injection solution (methanol:water 2:3, v:v). Hereafter, samples were centrifuged for 5.0 minutes at 18,213 g and 50 μL was injected into a Nexera SIL30ACMP (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) autosampler. Chromatographic separation was achieved using a Kinetex EVO 1.7 μm C18 column (2.1 mm id, 50 mm) (Phenomenex). A gradient protocol of two mobile phases containing water with 0.1% formic acid and 2 mM ammonium acetate, and methanol was applied at a flow rate of 0.6 mL/min. The gradient started at 50% methanol, which was gradually increased to 75% in 2.3 minutes. Next, the column was washed with 100% methanol for 0.5 minute before returning to the starting condition of 50% methanol for 0.7 minute. The assay had a total run time of 3.5 minutes. Tandem-mass spectrometry analysis was performed with a QTRAP6500+ instrument (Sciex, Concord, ON, Canada) operated in positive electrospray ionization mode (600°C) and multiple reaction monitoring mode. For quantitation of progesterone, mass-to-charge ratio (m/z) 287.1 \rightarrow 97.0 (androstenedione) and 294.1 \rightarrow 113.2 (androstenedione-d7) were monitored. In three serum pools containing 0.64, 1.5 and 1.7 nmol/L, total coefficient of variation (CV) was 10.9, 7.1 and 9.2%, respectively. The lower limit of quantitation was determined at 0.35 nmol/L (8.5%CV). Androstenedione was stable (90 – 110% recovery) in all tested storage conditions (seven days at 20 °C, two weeks in an RST tube at 4 °C and two weeks at – 20 °C). Furthermore, QC samples were stored at – 20 °C for prolonged periods (> 1 year). Hitherto, we have not observed instability issues under these storage conditions. The assay linearity showed a correlation coefficient (Spearman's correlation coefficient, $r^2 \geq 0.995$). Extraction recoveries was 96% and the matrix effect was 58%. No significant interference from epitestosterone, dihydrotestosterone, 17-hydroxyprogesterone, dehydro-epiandrosterone, estrone, estradiol, prednisone, prednisolone and abiraterone was detected. Furthermore, addition of 1 mmol/L hemoglobin, 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ bilirubin and 1% intralipid did not affect androstenedione quantitation. However, adding 1 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{L}$ of enzalutamide resulted in a 79.6% quantitation recovery for androstenedione.

Supplementary Figure 1. Box plots for SFQ Pain (A), SFQ Partner (B) and SFQ Enjoyment (C) scores at each follow-up moment after RRSO. Data was stratified for menopausal status (Black, premenopausal; Gray, postmenopausal). Significant pair-wise comparisons are indicated with * symbols (*, $p < 0.05$; **, $p < 0.01$; *, $p < 0.001$; ****, $p < 0.0001$).**

E1 = estrone

E2 = estradiol

SFQ = Sexual functioning questionnaire

T0 = Baseline

T1 = Six weeks

T2 = Seven months

Supplementary Figure 2. Spearman rho correlation matrix for correlations between changes in sex steroid levels and questionnaire scores. Correlation coefficients are color-coded at three levels from -1 (Blue) to 0 (White) to 1 (Red). Spearman's correlation coefficients that are significantly different from 0 ($\alpha=0.05$) are indicated with * symbols (*, $p<0.05$; **, $p<0.01$; ***, $p<0.001$; ****, $p<0.0001$).

E1 = estrone

E2 = estradiol

FACT = Functional assessment of cancer therapy

L = Lubrication

SFQ = Sexual functioning questionnaire

S = Sensation

T0 = Baseline

T1 = Six weeks

T2 = Seven months

